

NHSRAG: Addressing Multi-Hop Medical QA with Named-entity Heuristic Search Retrieval-Augmented Generation

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Abstract

Information retrieval is essential for multi-hop question answering (MHQA) as it's necessary for connecting relationships between entities. Answering complex, multi-hop biomedical questions often involves a trade-off between computational cost and accuracy. In our official MedHopQA leaderboard submission we chose a high-accuracy configuration that couples the proprietary Gemini-2.5-pro-preview-05-06 model with its built-in grounding via the Google Search API. This combination delivered our team's top exact-match (EM) score at 0.73. While effective, a fully-proprietary stack provide a straightforward path to high accuracy but at a high financial cost. On the other hand, popular Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) systems often require resource-intensive infrastructure, specifically semantic search, such as pre-built vector indexes, making it difficult to embed and query entire web-scale corpora like Wikipedia. as it is time-consuming and resource-intensive. Leveraging sparse index search with query decomposition technique using smaller, open-source language models is an alternative; implementing query decomposition with LM introduces computational overhead and requires high computational resources.

To offer a more accessible and efficient solution than previously discussed approaches, we propose NHSRAG, a Named-Entity Heuristic Search RAG pipeline. Our system avoids using resource-intensive modules for query decomposition by dynamically formulating its own search queries with entity extraction. Our approach applies Part-of-Speech (POS) tagging and noun-chunking to user questions to identify key medical concepts. These dynamically generated queries are used to retrieve context on-the-fly from the Wikipedia search API, which is then fed to a 4-bit quantized MedReason-8B model for answer generation. MedHopQA is the test set that includes biomedical knowledge from Wikipedia. When evaluated on the MedHopQA hidden test set, our NHSRAG pipeline achieved an exact match (EM) score of 0.43. We demonstrate a hybrid approach that significantly boosts performance, achieving a 0.47 EM score. This strategy selectively leverages the high-performance Gemini-2.5-pro-preview-05-06 model + grounding with Google Search API as a targeted fallback for complex questions where our primary system has insufficient information. This work validates NHSRAG as a low-cost pipeline for complex biomedical QA, significantly reducing financial barriers compared to proprietary models while also eliminating the overhead of creating a vector index or LLM-base query decomposition.

1. Introduction

Open-domain biomedical question answering has seen remarkable progress with the advent of Large Language Models (LLMs) [1, 2]. However, a frontier remains in solving *multi-hop* questions answering (MHQA), which require synthesizing facts from multiple documents to infer a correct answer [3]. Both QA and MHQA tasks are often solved by implementing popular Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG).

The BioCreative IX MedHopQA track addresses multi-hop reasoning by presenting **10,000 complex biomedical questions**, such as genes and rare diseases, that require connecting information across

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multiple Wikipedia pages; 1,000 of these are used for comparison between competitors [4].

State-of-the-art performance on such complex QA tasks is often dominated by large-scale, proprietary models like Google’s Gemini family, which leverage powerful web search capabilities for Effective Information Retrieval [5, 6].

For the official MedHopQA leaderboard we have submitted **Gemini-2.5-pro-preview-05-06** with Google Search grounding, achieving an EM of **0.73** the highest score among submissions at the time of writing. However, this run required approximately \$451 in API fees for a single run on the full dataset, rendering it impractical for many academic research groups and iterative development cycles.

The predominant open-source alternative, RAG with Dense Passage Retriever (DPR) for semantic search, typically relies on pre-built vector databases.[7] This paradigm involves a massive upfront cost of embedding an entire corpus—like Wikipedia—into dense vectors and maintaining specialized infrastructure for fast similarity searches using systems like FAISS or ScaNN.[8, 9]

Sparse index search is often implemented with query decomposition to break complex questions into simpler sub-queries. However, this technique frequently leverages resource-intensive Large Language Models [10, 11], leading to computational overhead. These approaches are resource-intensive and poorly suited for dynamic information environments or time-constrained challenges like MedHopQA.

To navigate the trade-offs between performance, cost, and implementation overhead, we propose **NHSRAG**: a *Name-entity Heuristic Search Retrieval-Augmented Generation* pipeline. Our system operates without a pre-built index. Instead we use NLP-driven query formulation and an external Wikipedia [12] search. We leverage spaCy [13] for POS tagging and noun-chunking to dynamically extract the noun term that are candidate medical entity concepts. These concepts generate targeted queries for the Wikipedia API , retrieving concise, high-relevance context. This context then feeds into a 4-bit quantized, biomedically-tuned open-source model, UCSC-VLAA/MedReason-8B [14, 15], for final reasoning.

Our contributions are threefold:

1. We introduce a lightweight RAG architecture that eliminates the significant preprocessing and storage costs associated with vector database indexing, making complex QA more accessible.
2. We design a dynamic, NLP-driven query formulation module using POS tagging to generate targeted search queries for multi-hop retrieval, without relying on an LLM.
3. We present an empirical analysis showing that our NHSRAG pipeline serves as a strong, cost-effective baseline (0.43 EM) and that its performance can be strategically enhanced to 0.47 EM through a hybrid approach that uses a powerful proprietary model as a targeted fallback.

Our work validates NHSRAG as a practical framework for complex biomedical MHQA, offering a pragmatic balance between resource efficiency and performance.

2. Related Work

Early biomedical QA benchmarks like BioASQ focused on single-document fact retrieval [16]. The field has since progressed to more complex multi-hop challenges, such as the current MedHopQA track, which require systems to synthesize information from multiple sources to answer a single question [3, 4].

Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) is one of the standard paradigm for such knowledge-intensive tasks, grounding LLM outputs in factual data to reduce hallucination [7]. High-performance RAG systems typically rely on pre-built dense vector indices using tools like FAISS for efficient search [8]. However, this indexing process is computationally expensive and requires significant storage, making it less agile for dynamic information sources [17].

To improve retrieval quality, recent work has focused on query decomposition, often using an LLM to break a complex question into simpler, searchable sub-queries [10, 11]. While powerful, this adds inference latency and can be unstable with quantized models. NHSRAG adopts this decompositional spirit but implements it with a fast, code-based heuristic using ‘spaCy’, ensuring reliability and speed.

Figure 1: End-to-end NHSRAG workflow. A user question is first processed by spaCy to extract a set of named entities. The named entity combinations form a query pool for the Wikipedia API. Retrieved page summaries are passed as context to the MedReason-8B model, which generates a structured short and long answer based on a high-constraint prompt template.

Finally, our work leverages recent advances in domain-specific LLMs. While models like Med-PaLM 2 have demonstrated expert-level performance [18], we utilize the open-source **UCSC-VLAA/MedReason-8B** [14], a powerful yet accessible model fine-tuned for biomedical reasoning. We benchmark this against the state-of-the-art proprietary model, **Gemini-2.5-pro-preview-05-06** [6], to situate our results within the current landscape of AI capabilities.

3. Proposed Method

To address the challenges of multi-hop biomedical question answering without relying on costly pre-built indexes, we designed and implemented the NHSRAG (Named-entity Heuristic Search Retrieval-Augmented Generation) pipeline. The modular system operates through stages designed to first build a highly relevant context and then use that context for answer synthesis. Figure 1 provides a high-level overview of this workflow.

3.1. Stage 1: Query Formulation

We developed a fast entity extraction module that analyzes the user’s question to formulate a set of search queries.

Dynamic Entity Extraction. The initial step is to identify the core concepts within the input question q . We process the question text using the spaCy NLP library with its lightweight English model, `en_core_web_sm` [13]. This model performs POS tagging and We extract candidate search terms by identifying noun chunks.

Query Pool Generation. We then refine the list of extracted entities to create a "query pool" for retrieval. We achieve this by first filtering common interrogative words, then remove the duplicate entities. To facilitate multi-hop reasoning, we generate new, combined queries by creating all possible pairs from the for each noun. The final query pool is limited to the 5 first combination of queries to balance retrieval breadth with API latency.

Input Question:

Which autoimmune disease is associated with chronic hives and can lead to dry mouth and dry eyes?

spaCy - Extracted Entities (Noun Chunks):

["autoimmune disease", "chronic hives", "dry mouth", "dry eyes"]

Generated Query Pool (5 query):

["autoimmune disease chronic hives", "autoimmune disease dry mouth", "chronic hives dry mouth", "autoimmune disease", "chronic hives"]

Successful Retrieval Example:

[Retrieval] Found page: "Xerostomia"

Figure 2: Example of the NLP-driven query formulation process. Key noun chunks are extracted from the user question and then combined to form targeted, multi-hop search queries for the Wikipedia API.

3.2. Stage 2: Wikipedia Article Retrieval

Next, the pipeline retrieves evidence from live Wikipedia API [12]. For each query that returns a valid Wikipedia page, we extract only the whole summary section. This both provide context for the LLM.

3.3. Stage 3: Answer Generation and Parsing

We use the quantized LLM with default Hugging-face generation configuration to answer the question based on the provided context.

Model Selection and Quantization. Our reasoning engine is the **UCSC-VLAA/MedReason-8B** model, an 8-billion-parameter LLM [14, 1]. This model was chosen for its fine-tuning on biomedical and achieve state-of-the-art in various Medical benchmark compare with others small size LLM. To make it computationally feasible, we load the model with 4-bit quantization setting ¹

High-Constraint Prompting. The assembled Wikipedia context and the original question are injected into a highly structured prompt template. We use "one-shot" prompting strategy with a fixed example, providing an example of a question, context, and a formatted 'Short Answer' and 'Long Answer' before presenting the input question and context. This method is more effective at enforcing the desired output structure (long and short answer) than a simple zero-shot instruction.

Inference and Fallback Strategy. In the generation step. A key characteristic of our system is its refusal to guess; if the retrieved context is insufficient to form a confident answer, the model's output is designed to be parsed as 'NaN'. For our final submission, these 'NaN' rows were handled by a **hybrid fallback mechanism**, where only these specific, difficult questions were sent to the Gemini-2.5-pro-preview-05-06 API for resolution and it will reduce cost to inference all questions with Gemini2.5 pro if we scale it further by using .

3.4. Experimental Setup

Data and Evaluation. We evaluate our system on the official MedHopQA hidden test set. All of the reported scores are the official Exact Match (EM) metric provided by the competition organizers.

¹we use 'bitsandbytes' library for LLM quantization. link: <https://github.com/bitsandbytes-foundation/bitsandbytes>

Systems for Comparison. We compare our primary NHSRAG pipeline with several configurations to understand the landscape of performance and cost:

- **Gemini-2.5-pro-preview-05-06 (Grounded):** A high-performance proprietary model with built-in web search, using a detailed Chain-of-Thought style prompt. This serves as our "upper-bound" baseline.
- **MedGemma-27B [19] (Zero-shot):** A large, 27B-parameter biomedical model tested with two prompts: a simple instruction ('prompt1') and a more detailed, structured instruction ('prompt2') to evaluate the impact of prompting on a model's without retrieval.
- **NHSRAG (MedReason-8B):** Our primary proposed system using the pipeline described in Section 3, *without* the hybrid fallback.
- **NHSRAG + Gemini Fallback:** Our hybrid system where the NHSRAG pipeline runs first, and any question it fails to answer ('NaN' result) is subsequently passed to the Gemini-2.5-pro-preview-05-06 API.

Cost Estimation. To provide a practical comparison of the different approaches, we estimated the financial cost of running each experiment on the full 10,000-question MedHopQA test set.

The cost for our proprietary baseline was calculated based on the official pricing for the Gemini-2.5-pro-preview-05-06 API used grounding with search (**35\$/ 1000 request**) [20]. The total inference cost for **10,000** questions was approximately **\$451 USD**.

We estimate the costs for our experiments based on the on-demand pricing for Google Colab Enterprise resources in the 'asia-southeast1' (Singapore) region [21]. The primary cost is the NVIDIA A100 80GB GPU, priced at approximately **\$5.57 per hour**. We used four concurrent runtimes for our experiments. The total estimated costs are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1

Cost and performance comparison across different experimental setups. Costs are estimated based on a rate of \$22.28/hour (4x A100 runtimes).

System Configuration	EM Score	Time (Hours)	Est. Cost (USD)
<i>Proprietary Baseline</i>			
Gemini-2.5-pro-preview-05-06 (Grounded)	0.73	62	~\$451.00
<i>Zero-Shot Baselines</i>			
MedGemma-27B (Detailed Prompt)	0.55	23	~\$512.00
MedGemma-27B (Simple Prompt)	0.47	19	~\$423.00
<i>Our Proposed Systems</i>			
NHSRAG (MedReason-8B)	0.43	12	~\$267.00
NHSRAG + Gemini Fallback	0.47	18	~\$313.00

The cost for the hybrid 'NHSRAG + Gemini Fallback' system is **\$313.00**, with **1,000 questions** that fallback to the Gemini API. However, the initial pass with the open-source NHSRAG pipeline remains highly cost-effective at approximately **\$267**. These demonstrate that our proposed pipeline offers a dramatic reduction of **47%** less than the MedGemma zero-shot approach and about **48.5%** price of the Gemini API approach; it is a financially viable option for academic research.

3.5. Results

Table 2 summarizes the performance of all evaluated systems on the hidden MedHopQA test set.

The proprietary Gemini-2.5-pro-preview-05-06 model sets the state-of-the-art performance at 0.73 EM, demonstrating the power of deeply integrated search and reasoning. In the zero-shot MedGemma-27B model shows strong performance based without using search retrieval, improving from 0.47 to 0.55 EM with better prompting alone. Our primary RAG pipeline, NHSRAG with the much smaller

Table 2

Main results on the hidden MedHopQA test set. Scores reflect the official Exact Match (EM) metric.

System Configuration	Exact Match (EM)
<i>Zero-Shot Baselines (Internal Knowledge Only)</i>	
MedGemma-27B (Simple Prompt, 'prompt1')	0.47
MedGemma-27B (Detailed Prompt, 'prompt2')	0.55
<i>Our Proposed Systems (Retrieval-Augmented)</i>	
NHSRAG (MedReason-8B)	0.43
NHSRAG + Gemini Fallback	0.47
<i>Proprietary Baseline (Grounding with Search)</i>	
Gemini-2.5-pro-preview-05-06	0.73

MedReason-8B model, achieved an EM score of 0.43. This result indicates that while the RAG framework is helpful, the overall performance is fundamentally capped by the quality of the ad-hoc retrieval; if insufficient context is found, it abstains from answering by parsed "NaN" in short answer and explain why it sufficient in long answer. In this test set, it performs insufficiently with context is 10%.

By using the NHSRAG pipeline as a low-cost first-pass filter and falling back to the Gemini-2.5-pro-preview-05-06 API for only the questions that resulted in a 'NaN' output, we achieved a final score of **0.47 EM**. This suggest that our hybrid system, built around a small 8B model, successfully **matches the performance of the 27B-parameter MedGemma model** while providing the benefits of a grounded, verifiable reasoning process for 90% of the questions. This demonstrates a competitive performance while drastically managing the costs associated with powerful proprietary APIs.

4. Discussion

Our experiments provide a clear overview of the current trade-offs in multi-hop biomedical QA. The state-of-the-art performance of Gemini 2.5 Pro (0.73 EM) highlights the significant advantage of large, proprietary models with deeply integrated web search. In the open-source domain, the strong zero-shot performance of MedGemma-27B (0.55 EM) confirms that substantial biomedical knowledge is encoded within its parameters, though this approach is inherently limited by its training data cutoff.

Our primary NHSRAG pipeline with MedReason-8B (0.43 EM) serves as a robust, RAG baseline. Its performance is fundamentally constrained by retrieval quality; our NLP-based query formulation, while effective, can sometimes fail to find the precise "bridging" documents required for complex multi-hop reasoning. In such cases, the system correctly abstains from answering rather than hallucinating, which results in a lower EM score but represents safer system behavior.

The most compelling result is from our hybrid system. By using NHSRAG as a low-cost first pass and falling back to Gemini 2.5 Pro for failed queries, we achieved a 0.47 EM score. This demonstrates that a lightweight 8B RAG system can effectively match the performance of a much larger 27B zero-shot model, while providing the verifiability of a retrieval-based approach. This hybrid strategy presents a pragmatic path forward, balancing the high cost of state-of-the-art APIs with the efficiency of open-source models. Future work should focus on improving retrieval, potentially by integrating a domain-specific reranker to better prioritize retrieved context.

5. Conclusion

In this work, we presented NHSRAG pipeline designed for efficient and accessible multi-hop biomedical question answering. Our system leverages dynamic, NLP-driven query formulation to retrieve context from Wikipedia for a quantized 8-billion-parameter model. While our pipeline established a robust baseline of 0.43 EM, our key contribution is the demonstration of a hybrid approach. By using our

cost-effective pipeline as a first-pass filter and falling back to a proprietary API for difficult cases, we achieved a competitive 0.47 EM score, matching the performance of a much larger zero-shot model. This validates NHSRAG as a practical framework and advocates for hybrid systems as a pragmatic strategy for balancing the high cost of state-of-the-art models with the performance requirements of complex QA tasks like MedHopQA.

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A. Prompt Templates

The structure and detail of the prompt significantly influenced model performance. We developed and tested several distinct prompt templates for our different experimental configurations. All prompts were designed to elicit a structured response containing a ‘Short Answer’ and a ‘Long Answer’.

A.1. NHSRAG Prompt for MedReason-8B (EM: 0.43)

For our primary RAG pipeline with MedReason-8B, we used a "one-shot" prompt. This template first provides a detailed system instruction and a perfect example of a question, context, and structured answer before presenting the new task. This high-constraint format proved most effective for ensuring the model adhered to the required output structure.

```
<s>[INST] <<SYS>>
```

```
You are a specialist biomedical AI assistant. Your only function is to receive a QUESTION and some CONTEXT, and then provide a structured answer. You must follow the format exactly. Do not add any conversational text, preamble, or your own thought process to the final output.
```

Your output must be structured as follows:

```
Short Answer: [A VERY CONCISE, direct answer, typically a single entity(e.g., disease name, gene name, "Yes", "No", a number, a chromosome), not a full sentence. Aim for under 60 characters if possible.]
```

```
Long Answer: [A detailed, formal explanation of the reasoning process, citing facts from the provided context pages.]
```

```
<</SYS>>
```

Here is an example.

```
**CONTEXT:**
```

```
---
```

```
Page: Neutrophil elastase
```

```
Summary: Neutrophil elastase (NE), also known as leukocyte elastase, is a serine protease in the same family as chymotrypsin and has a broad substrate specificity. Secreted by neutrophils during inflammation, it destroys bacteria and host tissue. It also has a role in degrading the virulence factors of bacteria.
```

```
---
```

```
Page: ELANE
```

```
Summary: Neutrophil elastase is an enzyme that in humans is encoded by the ELANE gene. The ELANE gene is located on the short arm of chromosome 11 at position 14. This protein is a member of the peptidase S1 family.
```

****QUESTION:****

Which human chromosome contains the gene that encodes the enzyme that can inactivate antithrombin?

[/INST]Short Answer: Chromosome 11

Long Answer: The context from the 'Neutrophil elastase' page indicates that neutrophil elastase is the enzyme that inactivates antithrombin. The context from the 'ELANE' page states that the ELANE gene encodes neutrophil elastase and is located on chromosome 11. Therefore, the answer is Chromosome 11.</s>

<s>[INST] Excellent. Now, using the same strict format, answer this new question based on the new context provided.

****CONTEXT:****

{wikipedia_context}

****QUESTION:****

{question_text}
[/INST]

A.2. MedGemma-27B Zero-Shot Prompts

To test the model without retrieval, we used two different zero-shot prompts with MedGemma-27B.

A.2.1. Simple Llama-2 Style Prompt (EM: 0.47)

This prompt provided basic instructions within a standard system-user format.

<s>[INST] <<SYS>>
You are a specialist biomedical AI assistant. Your only function is to receive a QUESTION and some CONTEXT, and then provide a structured answer. You must follow the format exactly. Do not add any conversational text, preamble, or your own thought process to the final output.

Your output must be structured as follows:

Short Answer: [A VERY CONCISE, direct answer, typically a single entity or yes/ no, not a full sentence.]

Long Answer: [A detailed, formal explanation of the reasoning process]
<</SYS>>

[INST] {question_text} [/INST]

A.2.2. Detailed Instructional Prompt (EM: 0.55)

This more verbose prompt yielded significantly better results by providing detailed, step-by-step instructions on how to reason and structure the output.

You are an expert biomedical researcher and question-answering system participating in the MedHopQA competition. Your goal is to answer the

provided QUESTION accurately, with a particular focus on providing a VERY CONCISE Short Answer.

QUESTION:
{question_text}

INSTRUCTIONS:

1. **Understand the Question:** Analyze the question to identify key entities and the information being sought.
2. **Reasoning:** Based primarily on the information retrieved from your searches, and supplemented by your internal knowledge where necessary, construct a step-by-step reasoning path to answer the question.
3. **Output Format:** Provide your answer strictly in the following format:

Short Answer: [Provide a VERY CONCISE, direct answer. This should ideally be a specific entity (e.g., disease name, gene name, "Yes", "No", a number, a chromosome). Avoid full sentences if a single entity or phrase suffices.]

Long Answer: [Your detailed explanation of how you arrived at the Short Answer. This explanation MUST:

- a. Clearly outline the reasoning steps or "hops" taken.
- b. Explicitly state the key facts derived from your internal search results that support each step of your reasoning.
- c. Maintain a formal, scientific tone.]

Do not include any preamble or introductory phrases before "Short Answer:".
Stick strictly to the Short Answer / Long Answer structure.

Begin answering the question now.

A.3. Gemini-2.5-pro-preview-05-06 Grounded Prompt (EM: 0.73)

For our proprietary baseline, we used a prompt that explicitly instructs the model to leverage its built-in search capabilities. It details a multi-step process of understanding, searching, reasoning, and then formatting the final output.

You are an expert biomedical researcher and question-answering system participating in the MedHopQA competition.

Your goal is to answer the provided QUESTION accurately, with a particular focus on providing a VERY CONCISE Short Answer.

You have inherent Google Search capabilities. You MUST leverage these capabilities to find relevant biomedical information to ground your answer.
The questions often require multi-hop reasoning.

QUESTION:
{question_text}

INSTRUCTIONS:

1. **Understand the Question:** Analyze the question to identify key entities and the information being sought.
2. **Perform Searches (Crucial):** Internally use your Google Search capability to find reliable biomedical information.
3. **Reasoning:** Based *primarily* on the information retrieved from your

searches, and supplemented by your internal knowledge where necessary, construct a step-by-step reasoning path to answer the question.

4. ****Output Format:**** Provide your answer strictly in the following format:

Short Answer: [Provide a VERY CONCISE, direct answer. This should ideally be a specific entity (e.g., disease name, gene name, "Yes", "No", a number, a chromosome). Avoid full sentences if a single entity or phrase suffices. Aim for under 60 characters if possible.]

Long Answer: [Your detailed explanation of how you arrived at the Short Answer. This explanation MUST:

- a. Clearly outline the reasoning steps or "hops" taken.
- b. Explicitly state the key facts derived from your internal search results that support each step of your reasoning.
- c. Maintain a formal, scientific tone.]

****Do not include any preamble or introductory phrases before "Short Answer:".****
****Stick strictly to the Short Answer / Long Answer structure.****

Begin answering the question now.